

Using Free Association of Words Method by Employing Flash Cards in Identifying Alternative Conceptions among Fourth Grade Students Studying Collins curriculum

Mohammad Nayef Ayasrah, Mohareb Ali Alsmadi, Shima' Mkhymryahyaa

Article Info

Article History

Received:
May 08, 2021

Accepted:
August 20, 2021

Keywords :

Free Association, Flash Cards, Scientific Alternative Conceptions, Collins Curriculum

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5228315

Abstract

The study aims to define the alternative scientific conceptions among fourth basic grade students studying Collins curriculum. To achieve the study objective, free association method was used by employing flash cards. The sample of the study consisted of (30) students of the fourth grade who are studying Collins curriculum at one school of Irbid governorate. The results of the study showed that students have alternative conceptions related to classifying living organisms, and having alternative conceptions for birds, mammals, reptiles, insects, fishes, relationships between organisms, and the food chain. The study also defined the number and percentages of students who have these conceptions. In light of the results the study suggest to use the scientific names of the living organisms in the textbook, and in the classroom, in addition to conducting future studies defines the alternative conceptions among students of the other school stages.

Introduction

It is important to provide learners with scientific conceptions in the primary stage; in aim to facilitate acquisition of concepts and science processes in the next stages. Although curricula in the different educational systems assured the necessity standardizing scientific terminology that indicates scientific conceptions to describe their distinctive characteristics, it has been found that some learners attends primary school and they are having life concepts they acquired through their interactions with the environment, watching cartoons and children's television programs. For example, learners say: "The snow melted", and they may complete the fourth basic grade describing fusion concept by melting, although teachers think that they have explained this concept accurately, and asked about it in the exams, they are surprised that some students still retaining what is known as "Alternative perceptions" of these concepts, which do not agree with the correct scientific interpretations of the concept.

Due to the importance of scientific conceptions, their significance role in teaching science, and the necessity to be taught correctly, investigating learners epistemological believes of the alternative perceptions of the scientific conceptions and defining them has received the interest of many researchers who generally agrees that learners attend the classroom with alternative perceptions and ideas about the scientific conceptions and natural phenomena. These perceptions in lots of times contradict with the scientific perception that learners supposed to acquire, these perceptions are common in the different learning stages especially in in the different disciplines of science, which are difficult to be changed and replaced as they effect learning (Yeo &Zandnik, 2001). Additionally, the process of defining these conceptions and correcting them is one of the main factors that affect students learning of the scientific conceptions correctly (Gonen&Kocakaya, 2010).

Students' alternative perceptions form as a result of their own attempt to interpret new knowledge based on their previous knowledge and experiences, which could be formed in a wrong way or it may lacks accurate knowledge of the concept's defining features. Furthermore, teacher may lead inadvertently to create these alternative perceptions in the learners when he provides unsuccessful examples or similes; or uses his slang language in the learning context, such as using the word "Atom" to refer to the ant and at the same time to refer for as the smallest part of matter (Al-Zahrany, 2019).

Constructivism emphasizes the importance of context in the process of acquiring conceptions, the importance of exploring the learner's prior knowledge, and the active interaction between the learner and the learning material; as the learner organizes what he learns into interconnected structures called conceptual structures, which are stored in the memory and can be retrieved and used (Major &Mangope, 2012). Learning, as Piaget points out, involves the interaction between the learner structures and the new ideas within the process of accommodation and assimilation. Accommodation process takes place through the incorporation and

assimilation of new information with the previous one in the student conceptual structure, where pre-misconceptions called alternative conceptions may form (Krause, Kelly, Corkins&Tasooji, 2009). In assimilation, new information and conceptions that are different from the learner's conceptual structure are acquired, which need to adjust the nature of the learner's conceptual structure to be able to deal with the new ideas and conceptions in the context of recognizing the distinctive features of the conception (Fonsnot& Perry, 1996). Additionally, it is worth noting that if learner is able to solve the problems he faces in light of the conceptual structures he has, then he will not feel the need to change them, even if these structures did not succeed in solving some problems successfully, where the learner may resort to making some simple changes on the conceptions in his conceptual structure, where the learner perform accommodation process without the need for assimilation process (Posner, Hewson&Gertzog, 1982).

Nevertheless, teachers must emphasize the distinct characteristics of a concept which helps learners performing assimilation process to adjust the alternative conceptions within planned learning situations, as neglecting alternative perceptions and not correcting them may lead to impeding the new learning process, for example a student may refuse the new information because it contradict his alternative perceptions, and therefore learning does not happen as planned; or a student may integrate the new knowledge with his alternative perceptions, consequently, he has a distorted cognitive structure, and thus weak learning outcomes that are inconsistent with the curriculum objectives (Krause, Kelly, Corkins&Tasooji, 2009).

Researchers noted that the content of the newly applied science curricula for the fourth basic grade for the school year 2019/2020 (Pilot edition) by Harper Collins Publishers is rich with scientific conceptions that need an effective teaching method that stimulates students' motivation and attract their attention, as the research team surveyed through an interview the perceptions of a sample of (10) science teachers who teaches this curriculum and (3) educational supervisors. The interview concluded that the curriculum contains many scientific conceptions, where learners may possess alternative preconceptions lacking some defining characteristics of the concept, for this reason, it is important for science teacher to be aware of the students' alternative perceptions to be not ignored in the learning context, and to develop the scientific conceptions accurately among students, this needs from teachers to use reliable strategies able to diagnose the alternative perceptions and reveal. By reviewing previous literature and studies concerning the most effective methods for the targeted age group, it was found that free association method and by using flash cards is the most effective one. This method depends on the learner's expressing the conceptions he possess through using as much words and ideas in a relatively short time, which may help the teacher to reveal the embedded concepts in the learner's conceptual structure. Furthermore, teacher can use flash cards applications in free association of words method at the beginning of every learning unit to define the alternative perceptions of the conceptions included in it, then he prepares a set of cards, where the first side shows a picture, name or symbol for one of the conceptions included in the targeted unit, while the other side shows the term indicating the concept so that it includes the defining characteristics of a concept. At the beginning, the teacher shows students the first side of the card through the application, and he asks every one of them to express this concept in written words by using the largest number of sentences and ideas, and then he show them the other side which contains the correct ideas about the concept, after that he asks students to compare what they wrote (Personal perception about the concept) with what is shown on the card. The teacher may also use this method after the class as a form of reliable evaluation; thus, the teacher has employed technology in diagnosing alternative perceptions with minimal time and effort, and enabled learners to practice self-evaluation process by modifying their conceptual structure in light of the new experience.

Previous Studies

Doglas and Cathy (2000) study aimed to use free association in defining the cognitive structure related to (6) scientific conceptions among (30) middle stage students in an American school, by asking a set of questions about the concepts and giving the students the opportunities to response. The results of the study showed that there is a difference in the scientific conceptions among the study sample. It also showed that (77.2%) of the study sample have alternative scientific conceptions. While Steven and Jakobo (2010) study tried to reveal the conceptions possessed by (54) university students studying biology in America by using free association method of evolution concept, through asking a question about the evolution definition from their perspective's and write it down. The study found that (70%) of the students have alternative conceptions about the origin of human and his and development. The study recommended the necessity to define the alternative conceptions in the different disciplines of science.

In another study, Matar (2010) discussed the effectiveness of electronic blogs in addressing alternative scientific conceptions among (55) ninth grade students at Gaza in Palestine. A diagnostic test was developed to define the alternative conceptions students possess. The study indicated that these concepts are common among the study sample by (80%). It also revealed the effectiveness of electronic blogs in adjusting these concepts.

Kelly (2011) sought to define the effectiveness of flash cards in revealing biological conceptions among a sample of (36) students in the basic grades at Florida state, USA. A set of flash cards were presented to the students and they were asked about the conceptions in them, and to compare the conceptions they mentioned

before presenting the flash cards to them. Results showed that using flash cards lead to the increase in the number of conceptions that students remember compared to their number before using flash cards. The study recommends using flash cards as a diagnostic method and evaluation of learning.

In Saudi Arabia, Alshaya and Alharbi (2011) aimed to reveal the alternative conceptions among a sample of (184) high school students at Riyadh about material, its states and transformations through a test prepared at York University in the United Kingdom. The study showed that students possess several alternative conceptions such as confusing between the concepts of fusion and melting dissolution, it also showed that traditional teaching methods is one of the main reasons for this.

While Aldahmash (2014) study in Al-Yemen aimed to define the alternative conceptions possessed by (56) students from the seventh basic grade about matter and its attributes by using a diagnostic test. It was found that students possess alternative conceptions about concept of the study. The study suggested activating the role of scientific experiments in teaching science.

Carrie and Kristy (2017) conducted a study about the use of free association in student learning assessment for some scientific conceptions. The study showed that free association one of the effective methods of assessing students understanding.

In another study by Mensour (2018) in Algeria he tried to define the alternative conceptions among fourth grade students related to some of physics conceptions through a diagnostic test applied on (91) male students and (114) female students. The study concluded that alternative conceptions common among (46%) of the students. The study showed that teachers are the main reasons for their existence from the students 'point of view by a percent of (53%), then the textbook by a percent of (21%).

Through reviewing the previous studies it can be noted that there is an interest in studying the alternative conceptions among students, the studies used diagnostic tests to reveal these conceptions. Additionally, it can be noted that students possess alternative conceptions in the different school stages. Thus, this study tried to use free association as a reliable evaluation method in revealing alterative conceptions among students by using flash cards includes pictures from Collins textbook.

1. STUDY PROBLEMS & QUESTIONS

Learner possessing of alternative conceptions within his cognitive structure is considered as a main factor for accurate thinking. The teaching process that is based on understanding and realizing the concepts, and then understanding the relationships between them is considered as the process required reaching a meaningful understanding that enables student to interact effectively with his environment (Boutros, 2017).

Furthermore, learner possession of conceptions that does not conform with the correct scientific knowledge (Alternative conceptions) is considered as an impediment to achieving the objectives of the educational learning process in the basic stage in Jordan, which is understanding and thinking; combining science and work; theory and application; analysis and planning; opening horizons for students to engage in every profession, craft or art (Ministry of Education, 2019).

Also, measuring students' performance is one of the quality indicators related to the system's results in the national and international assessments. Internationally, Jordan participates in TIMSS and PISA tests, and seeks to improve the Jordanian students' results in these tests (Ministry of Education, 2019).

Due to the decline in fourth grade students' performance in science in TIMSS international tests, as the results did not get to the international levels required for the classification intervention (<http://www.timss.org/>), the National Center for Curriculum Development has changed the science books for the fourth basic grade, by assigning the British publishing house Collins, starting from the 2019/2020 school year.

Students' possession for alternative scientific conceptions impedes proper understanding and forms a fragile cognitive structure. Also, forming these concepts and their continued existence after students' undergo with the educational experience is more dangerous, which was evident in TIMSS tests results. Furthermore, traditional teaching methods are unable to reveal these conceptions or modifying them. Thus, free association and flash cards gives the opportunities for teachers to reveal these conceptions in a more comprehensive and clear manner.

Questions of the study

- 1- What are the alternative conceptions do fourth-grade students have
- 2- Is there any statistically significant differences ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the alternative scientific conceptions of the fourth grade students in light of gender?"

2. STUDY OBJECTIVES & IMPORTANCE

. The study aims to define the alternative scientific conceptions among fourth basic grade students studying Collins curriculum.

The importance of the study is represented in the following:

- Shed the light on the importance of alternative conceptions among fourth grade students, the reasons for their existence, and how to modify them.

- Employing free association method and flash cards are considered one of the unconventional methods to enhance the students learning and achieve the learning material objectives.
- This is the first study in Jordan that sought to define the alternative scientific conceptions among fourth grade students after employing the modern curriculum (Collins).
- This study may provide decision makers in the ministry of education with results that contribute in curriculum development.
- Pictures and drawings included in the book were used, which may lead to evaluating these pictures achievement to its objectives.
- The study may guide researchers to conduct other studies related to curriculum development.

4.THEROTICAL FRAMEWORKS & METHODS

4.1 Study Terms

- Free Association: Is a method where the student is given a specific concept, then he is asked to present all his ideas about the main concept and express them by using his own language (Brain Storming).
- Flash Cards: Cards that present the concept to be learned or evaluate the extent of its learning. In this study the pictures included in "Living Organisms and its Classification" unit were presented on these cards.
- Alternative Conceptions: The ideas and concepts that students have about the living organisms in the environment, which are not consistent with the correct scientific understanding that students have expressed through free association.
- Science Subject: The fourth grade book approved by the Ministry of Education in all schools of Jordan starting from the school year 2019/2020, and it is one of Collins series books in Science.

4.2Study Limitations

- The study was restricted to fourth-grade students who are learning using Collins series books for the school year 2019/2020.
- The study was restricted to the second unit "Living Organisms and its Classification" of the science subject (Collins series), which have been started teaching in this year.
Data accuracy depends on concepts comprehensiveness presented by the sample of the study through their responses on the individual interviews questions.

4.3 StadyApproach

To achieve the study objectives which is defining the alternative conceptions among fourth grade students, descriptive analytical design was used, by describing the study phenomenon and analyzing it in aim to define its causes.

4.4 Study Population .

The **study population** consisted of (7051) fourth grade students enrolled in the public education at Irbid governorate in the academic year 2019/2020.

4.5 study sample

The **study sample** consisted of (30) male and female students' selected using simple random method from one of the public schools at Irbid governorate.

Study Instrument

4.6Study Instrument

Alternative Conceptions Diagnostic Test

The instrument of the study consisted of an alternative conceptions diagnostic test, where the test was developed after analyzing the content of the selected unit from the fourth grade science book "Living Organisms and its Classification", to define the scientific concepts presented in this unit. Content analysis validity was verified by distributing the instrument on (7) experts at Al-Balqa'a Applied University specializing in curricula and instructional methods, educational supervisors of science. Analysis reliability was investigated by calculating the agreement percentage and disagreement, as two researchers from the research team analyzed individually. Inter-rater reliability percentage was calculated and it was (0.86). After investigating analysis validity and reliability, flash card was wording for each concept. It included pictures for the concepts included in "Living Organisms and its Classification" unit of the study that the researchers used in the free association procedures.

4.7 validity of Instrument :Test validity was investigated by distributing the test on the same experts; internal consistency was also checked by calculating correlation between items and the total scores by applying it on a pilot sample consisted of (30) students from outside original targeted sample. Internal consistency percentages ranged between (0.74-0.88).

4.8 Reliability of Instrument : The reliability of the test was also verified using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, and it reached (0.75). Also, its stability was verified using the split-half method, where the stability coefficient after it was corrected was (0.82). These are appropriate values for the current study.

4.9 Study Variables

- Independent variable: Free Association of Words Method by Employing Flash Cards.
- Dependent variable: Alternative Conceptions.

4.10 Study Procedures

To achieve the study objectives, the following were done:

- 1- The administration of the selected school has been contacted to obtain approval for conducting the study.
- 2- The teacher who teaches science for the students who is enrolled in this study has been contacted.
- 3- After informing the teacher about the purpose of the study, it have been agreed to select the second unit from the fourth grade science subject "Living Organisms and its Classification", as it was selected after discussing the teacher about the most common alternative conceptions among the fourth grade students.
- 4- The second unit has been analyzed in aim to prepare a list including the scientific concepts exist in it.
- 5- Pictures of the book were approved and prepared as flash cards.
- 6- Each card included a short question "Appendix (1)".
- 7- The card and the questions have been presented to a set of specialist to check their validity, as they made some opinions, which were taken into consideration.
- 8- Interviews were made with each student individually, the card and the questions were presented in a way enables them to provide everything they know about the concept by using the free association method. Students were informed that this has no impact on their school grades, and that the aim of this is only to have a dialogue with them and to help them form the correct scientific concepts.
- 9- The recorded data was transcribed, and the concepts were detected for each student.

3. STUDY RESULTS, DISCUSSIONS , RECOMMENDATIONS&CONCLUSION

3.1 Results & Discussions

First Question: "What are the alternative conceptions do fourth-grade students have?"

To answer this question, voice recorded data and paper data collected through the students' interviews were transcribed. After that, students' responses were evaluated by the research team and science teacher; to categorize students' responses and define the accurate conceptions and alternative conceptions, as seen in table (1).

Table 1.Number of Students who has Alternative Conceptions, and Defining these Conceptions in "Classifying Living Organisms" Unit

Scientific Conceptions	Number of Students who has Alternative Conceptions	Alternative Conceptions
Birds	27	There is no distinction between eagle and falcon "Picture (1) and picture (6), Appendix (1)"
	26	Penguin is not a bird "Picture (3), Appendix (1)"
Mammals	25	All mammals lives in the land "Picture (1) and Picture (2), Appendix (1)"
	10	The camel is a predator "Picture (1), Appendix (1)"
	25	Dolphin is not a mammal "Picture (2), Appendix (1)"
Amphibians	2	Amphibians breathe by gills "Picture (4), Appendix (1)"
	25	Crocodile is an amphibians "Picture (2), Appendix (1)"
Reptiles	10	Reptiles are harmful and not beneficial organisms to humans "Picture (3) and Picture (4), Appendix (1)"
Fish	9	Fish are pets that do not harm humans "Picture (1) and Picture (2), Appendix (1)"
	25	The fish in picture (4) "Appendix (1)" is Nemo
Insects	30	The creature in picture (3) "Appendix (1)" is Mantis
	27	The creature in picture (3) "Appendix (1)" bigger than the mouse

	20	Bee is a bird not an insect "Picture (5), Appendix (1)"
	28	The creature in picture (5) "Appendix (1)" is Ladybug
Relationships between living Beings	22	Fox is called a prey "Picture (6), Appendix (1)"
	25	Predation is rivalry "Picture (6), Appendix (1)"
Food Chain	22	Rabbit do not eat mouse "Picture (7), Appendix (1)"
	27	Jackal is another name for wolf "Picture (7), Appendix (1)"

By reviewing table (1), the following can be noted:

Firstly: Birds Concept

(27) students with a percent of (90%) of the total number unable to distinguish between eagle and falcon. This can be referred to the fact that these organisms in the Jordanian environment to a large extent, which have not been clarified in picture (1) and picture (6) "Appendix (1)". It also can be attributed to the fact that teachers does not emphasize on the distinctive features between eagle and falcon, since they have a major role in anticipating alternative scientific conceptions for students to try to avoid them.

Penguin is not classified as a bird by (26) students with a percent of (86.6%). Students mentioned in their responses that it doesn't fly and for that it is not a bird, but when asked about chicken they responded that it is a bird, although it doesn't fly, explaining their response to the fact that chicken is small and fly a little, but penguin is heavy and large.

This result can be attributed to the fact that the ability to fly is the main criterion for students in classifying birds, although when defining birds in the school subjects, this criterion was not set. School subjects defined birds as an animal mostly covered by feathers, have legs and peak, reproduces by eggs, and most of them have wings. In addition, this can be attributed to the fact that most books do not include organisms that are classified as birds, although it is not, such as ostrich, or because the teacher does not concentrate on that while presenting the learning material.

Secondly: Mammals

(25) students with a percent of (83.3%) had an alternative conception related to the whereabouts of mammals which is always land. This can be attributed to mammals definition included in the book (page 8) which defines it as an animal covered by hair or fur, cold-blooded, reproduces by birth, and nurses its babies (ex. monkeys, elephants, horses, lions). This made some students generalize this information to all mammals, for example one of the students said: "Bat is a bird, because it is in the sky", while another said: "Dolphin is not a mammal, it lives in the sea".

(10) students with a percent of (33%) had an alternative conception related to camel, which is a predator. This is due to personal experiences of these students in which they were attacked by a camel while they were in touristic places. For example, one student said: "It was going to attack me and eat my finger", another one said "When I touch it, it attacked me", and another said: "I thought it was a pet, but I found it is savage, I fear it, it ran after me".

(25) students with a percent of (83.3%) had an alternative conception related to the dolphin categorization, which is not a mammal. Researchers noticed that students who have this alternative conception are those who have an alternative conception that mammal lives only on the land. For example, a student said: "Dolphin is a fish because it lives in the water". Researchers also noticed that this alternative conception entailed alternative conceptions about dolphin traits, as one of the students said: "Dolphin lives in the sea, which means that it reproduces by eggs", and another one said: "Dolphin has gills".

Thirdly: Amphibians

(27) students with a percent of (90%) had an alternative conception concerning the way amphibians breath, which is gills, and that because they live in the water "Amphibians have gills because they live in water". This can be referred to the fact that students unable to distinguish between amphibious and non-amphibious organisms, and to the lack of diversification in the book's examples and being satisfied with the frog, "Picture (4), Appendix (1)".

(25) students with a percent of (83.3) had an alternative conception concerning crocodile classification, which is amphibians. Although it was mentioned in the book as a reptile "Picture (2), Appendix (1)". This is because students concentrate on the creature ability to be in the water and on the land as the main trait of amphibians. For example, a student said: "Crocodile goes into water and land, then it is an amphibian", and another one said: "if the animal lives in the land and in the water, then it is an amphibian".

It should be noted here that when the teacher is informed of this result, she brought the exam papers of the students who had this understanding, to be surprised that they responded to the question related to crocodile as an amphibians correctly, which emphasize an important characteristic for alternative conceptions, that it resist change; that students change it momentarily and then return to it (Asmar, 2008). For that, teacher must follow constructivist teaching approach not behavioral teaching approach in assessing the apparent behavior.

Fourthly: Reptile

(10) students with a percent of (33%) had an alternative conception about the uselessness of reptiles to humans, they explained this by the fact that it eats humans such as crocodile, as one of the students said: "Crocodile is wild, it eats people". One of the students faced a situation where he has been exposed to a snake in the house, he said that it sting, he said: "One, a snake was going to kill be by its venom".

This confirms the concept "Knowledge, Technology and Society", included in the previous school subjects, which may mention that snakes venom was used to make various medicinal drugs to heal people, while Collins Science Series did not mention this important part.

Fifthly: Fish

(9) students with a percent of (30%) had an alternative conception indicates that fish is a pet that do not harm humans. Although, a shark was shown, "Picture (1) and Picture (2), Appendix (1)".

(25) students called the name "Nemo" "Picture (4), Appendix (1)".

"Don't you know Nemo??!!!"

"Nemo, sure".

Students gave "Nemo" the human characteristics

"Nemo thinks how he can find his father".

"Nemo who sang a song with his father".

This result can be attributed to the fact that children have watched and got attached to "Finding Nemo" movie, which won an Academy Award in 2003 (<https://ar.wikipedia.org/wik>). Thus, we must take into account the impact of animation on children, although this movie has been viewed (17) years ago, it still affect children, this emphasize the role of audio and visual media in enabling students to form concepts and embrace it in school life (Al-Momani&Dowlat, 2011).

Sixth: Insects

(30) students with a percent of (100%) called mantodea a mantis "Picture (3), Appendix (1)", which is the known name for this insect. Thus, students have used the known name and did not know the scientific name of it. Also, it should be noted that that the teacher also used the known name, and the book did not request for the scientific name for this insect when it was presented, nor did it write it in the learning material.

The known name of this insect is "Mantis", which means in Arabic "Horse", and that lead (10) student to categorize it as a mammal.

(27) students with a percent of (90%) saw the manrodea bigger than the mouse. This is attributed to the picture size "Picture (3), Appendix (1)" compared to the mouse picture "Picture (2), Appendix (1)".

(20) students with a percent of (66.6%) classified bee as a bird not an insect, due to its ability to fly. It can be noted that "Picture (4), Appendix (1)" included crawling insects, except for the bees. This indicates the importance to include flying insects in the book, and highlighting the apparent differences between birds and insects by teachers, which may not be achieved by traditional teaching methods, as it needs a constructive teaching method to enable students to build concepts, linking and distinguishing between them (Abu Hola& Al-Meteary, 2010).

(28) students with a percent of (93.3%) called coccinellidoe as ladybug "Picture (4), Appendix (1)", which is the known name that the student hears for this insect. Although, the book mentioned the known scientific name "Coccinellidoe", however the teacher did not stress the necessary to use the scientific name and presenting it in the lesson or the exams.

Seventh: Relationships between Living Organisms

(22) students with a percent of (73%) called the fox a prey "Picture (5), Appendix (1)". This may be indicated to the fact that the arrow goes from the chicken towards the fox, this have been explained by (5) students as meaning that the chicken is the predator and the fox is the prey. For example, a student said: "This is because the arrow goes from the chicken", another student said: "The arrow goes from the chicken towards the fox". (7) students indicated that the number of chicken is bigger and thus they win on the lonely fox in the picture. For example a student said: "There are three chickens and one fox", and another said: "the fox is by himself". While the rest of the students were unable to distinguish between the two concepts "Prey and Predatory", and for that their responses were changing and unstable when defining these two concepts.

(24) students with a percent of (80%) did not distinguish between the concept of predation and rivalry "Picture (5), Appendix (1)". Researchers attribute this result to the ambiguous differences between the two concepts in the book, where it defined predation as the relationship between two living organisms; one is a predator feeding on the other, while the other is the prey. While rivalry is a hostile relationship as a result of mutual use of limited natural resources in the ecosystem, the word "Hostile" is unclear and do not highlight the difference between predation and rivalry.

Eighth: Food Chain

(22) students with a percent of (73.3%) mentioned that rabbit does not eat mouse. Students attributed this to the fact that they had never seen rabbit eating a mouse. A student said: "The rabbit never ate a mouse", another one said: "I never saw a rabbit eats a mouse". This also can be attributed to the fact that in cartoons they always see rabbits eat carrots, one student said: "Rabbits always love carrots", and his peer said: "Rabbits only

eat carrots". The responses of (5) students need attention as they state that mice are the ones that eat rabbits, where they saw this in the farms of their relatives. A student said: "Actually, the rabbits run away from the mouse", and another said: "The mouse attacks the rabbit, I saw it". Specialized biologist confirmed that mouse is the real enemy for rabbits, and that they prey them on their farms.

(27) students with a percent of (90%) referred to Jackal as another name for wolf. This could be a result for the similarity between picture (6) and picture (7) "Appendix (1)".

Second Question: "Is there any statistically significant differences ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the alternative scientific conceptions of the fourth grade students in light of gender?"

To answer this question, numbers and percentages of males and females students who have alternative scientific conceptions were defined. Mann-Whitney Nonparametric Test was used to compare between iterations of alternative conceptions between male and female students, as seen in table (2).

Table 2. Mann-Whitney Nonparametric Test to examine differences between the number of male and female students who have alternative conceptions

Scientific Conceptions	Number of Students who has Alternative Conceptions	Alternative Conceptions
Birds	27	There is no distinction between eagle and falcon "Picture (1) and picture (6), Appendix (1)"

Table (2):

Concept	Scientific Concept	Number of Students who have Alternative Conceptions				
		Gender	Number	%	Mann-Whitney Value	Sig.
Birds	There is no distinction between eagle and falcon "Picture (1) and picture (6), Appendix (1)"	Male	13	48%	0.037	0.847
		Female	14	52%		
	Penguin is not a bird "Picture (3), Appendix (1)"	Male	13	50%	84.5	1.00
		Female	13	50%		
Mammals	All mammals lives in the land "Picture (1) and Picture (2), Appendix (1)"	Male	13	52%	0.040	0.841
		Female	12	48%		
	The camel is a predator "Picture (1), Appendix (1)"	Male	5	50%	12.5	1.00
		Female	5	50%		
	Dolphin is not a mammal "Picture (2), Appendix (1)"	Male	10	40%	0.000	0.000*
		Female	15	60%		
Amphibians	Amphibians breathe by gills "Picture (4), Appendix (1)"	Male	13	48%	0.037	0.847
		Female	14	52%		
	Crocodile is an amphibians "Picture (2), Appendix (1)"	Male	15	54%	0.143	0.705
		Female	13	46%		
Reptiles	Reptiles are harmful and not beneficial organisms to humans "Picture (3) and Picture (4), Appendix (1)"	Male	5	50%	12.5	1.00
		Female	5	50%		
Fish	Fish are pets that do not harm humans "Picture (1) and Picture (2), Appendix (1)"	Male	12	48%	0.040	0.841
		Female	13	52%		
	The fish in picture (4) "Appendix (1)" is Nemo	Male				
		Female				
Insects	The creature in picture (3) "Appendix (1)" is Mantis	Male	15	50%	112.5	1.00
		Female	15	50%		
	The creature in picture (3) "Appendix (1)" bigger than the mouse	Male	14	50%	98.00	1.00
		Female	14	50%		
	Bee is a bird not an insect "Picture (5), Appendix (1)"	Male	14	50%	98.00	1.00
		Female	14	50%		
	The creature in picture (5) "Appendix (1)" is Ladybug	Male				
		Female				
Relationships between living organisms	Fox is called a prey "Picture (6), Appendix (1)"	Male	12	55%	0.182	0.670
		Female	10	45%		
	Predation is rivalry "Picture (6),	Male	13	52%	0.040	0.841

	Appendix (1)"	Female	12	48%		
Food Chain	Rabbit do not eat mouse "Picture (7), Appendix (1)"	Male	12	55%	0.182	0.670
		Female	10	45%		
	Jackal is another name for wolf "Picture (7), Appendix (1)"	Male	14	52%	0.037	0.847
		Female	13	48%		

Table (2) shows that the percentages of male students who possess alternative conceptions are equal to the percentages of female students who possess alternative conceptions, based on the results of frequencies, the values of Mann-Whitney Nonparametric Test, and the statistically significance level, as they all were higher than (0.05).

The previous result shows no difference in the scientific alternative conceptions among fourth grade students in light of gender. Researchers attribute this result to the fact that male and female students participated in the learning material, and in the teaching method. Also, the students' lives in the same society, thus, they used the same known names of some insects, or the names used in cartoons they have watched. Table (2) also shows that male students have higher percent of scientific alternative conceptions than females (ex. Dolphin is not a mammal "Picture (2), Appendix (1)", Crocodile is an amphibians "Picture (2), Appendix (1)"). This result can be explained by the fact that students concentrate on the place where the creature lives when classifying it into groups of living organisms (ex. Dolphin lives in the sea, which means that it reproduces by eggs), this is due to students impulsive in generalizing the results based on the common traits in the concepts as they are classified within the main concept (Zayton, 2014).

This result is consistent with the results of the studies of Doglas and Cathy (2000), Steven and Jakobo (2010) and Matar (2010) in the prevalence of alternative conceptions among students in the different school levels. It is also consistent with the results of Kelly (2011) study in the role of flash cards as a diagnostic mean for students' concepts and cognitive structure; the study of Alshaya and Alharbi (2011) in the importance to use constructivist teaching approach in learning and quitting the traditional teaching methods, and Mensour (2018) study results in the role of teachers in students' possessing alternative conceptions.

4.2 Conclusion

The effectiveness of the free association strategy through the use of flashcards in revealing the concepts of alternative science and the cognitive structure of fourth-grade students studying the Collins curriculum in science.

4.3 Recommendations

In light of the results, the study recommends:

- 1- Use of the scientific names for the living organisms in the school subjects.
- 2- Teachers' use of the scientific names of living organisms in teaching.
- 3- Teachers' employ for pictures of the textbook in teaching.
- 4- Pointing for the living organisms exist in the student's environment.
- 5- Adoption the key attributes in defining living organisms groups.
- 6- Using teacher-trusted assessment methods.
- 7- Focusing on the importance of revealing the alternative conceptions among students before and after the lesson.
- 8- Organizing workshops about the importance of free association and flash cards as a diagnosis assessment method.
- 9- Conducting future studies addressing the role of free association and flash cards in defining the alternative conceptions of students in different school level.

4. References

- Abu Hola, M. & Al-Metear, M. (2010). The effect of a computerized instructional programme on changing the alternative conceptions in science among second intermediate grade students in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. *Damascus University Journal for Educational and Psychological Sciences*, 26(4), 347-389.
- Aldahmash, A. (2014). The effect of alternative low cost experiments on seventh grade students' alternative and misconceptions of concepts related to matter and its properties and states. *Journal of Educational and Psychological Sciences*, 15(1), 179-206.
- Al-Momani, M. & Dowlat, A. (2011). The effect of using scientific animation in teaching science on students' acquisition of scientific concepts. *Damascus University Journal for Educational Sciences*, 27(3), 647-680.

- Alshaya, F. & Alharbi, A. (2011). Misconceptions about the States of Matter among 12th Grade's in Riyadh City. *Dirasat: Educational Sciences*, 38(5), 1750-1765.
- Al-Zahrany, S. (2019). *Flash Cards to define the alternative perceptions of the learners*. Retrieved from: <https://www.new-educ.com/flash-cards-%D9%88-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%AA%D8%B5%D9%88%D8%B1%D8%A7%D8%AA-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%A8%D8%AF%D9%8A%D9%84%D8%A9>
- Asmar, R. (2008). *The effect of learning cycle to modify the alternative perception of scientific concepts and their attitudes towards it for the primary sixth grade students*. Unpublished Master Thesis, Islamic University of Gaza, Palestine.
- Carrie, J., & Kristy, L. (2017). Using Word Associations as a Formative Assessment for Understanding Phylogenetics. *The American Biology Teacher*, 79,(8). 668–670.
- Douglas, N., & Cathy, M.(2000). What is free association and what does it measure?. *Memory & Cognition*, 28 (6), 887-899.
- Fosnot, C., & Perry, R. (1996). *Constructivism: A psychological theory of learning*. Constructivism: Theory, perspectives, and practice, 8-33.
- Jordanian Ministry of Education. (2019). *Science book for fourth grade (An experimental edition)*. London: Collins Science Series.
- Gönen, S., Kocakaya, S. 2010. A cross – Age study on the understanding of heat and temperature. *Eurasian J. Phys. Chem. Educ.*, 2 (1): 1-15. Retrieved from <http://www.ijpce.org/index.php/IJPCE/article/view/116>
- Kelly, G. (2011). *An investigation of the effects of using digital flash cards to increase biology vocabulary knowledge in school students with learning disabilities*. A dissertation submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy. College of Education at the University of Central Florida. From: http://etd.fcla.edu/CF/CFE0003972/Grillo_Kelly_J_201108_PhD.pdf
- Krause, S., Kelly, J., Corkins, J., & Tasooji, A. (2009). *The Role of Prior Knowledge on the Origin and Repair of Misconceptions in an Introductory Class on Materials Science and Engineering*. In 3rd Research in Engineering Education International Conference.
- Major, T., & Mangope, B. (2012). The Constructivist Theory in Mathematics: The Case of Botswana Primary Schools. *International Journal Review of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 3(2), 139-147.
- Matar, M. (2010). *Effectiveness of a blog in the treatment of Misconceptions of scientific concepts of students in ninth grade and their attitudes towards it*. Unpublished Master Thesis, Islamic University of Gaza, Palestine.
- Mensour, M. (2018). Alternative conceptions of the physics concepts among fourth middle grade students. *Journal of Educational and Psychological Sciences*, 7(2), 428-449.
- Posner, G., Strike, K. Hewson, P. Gertzog, W. (1982). Accommodation of a scientific conception: Toward a theory of conceptual change. *Science Education* 66(2), 21 1-227.
- Steven ,R.,Jakobi.(2010).Little “Little Monkeys on the Grass...” How People for and Against Evolution Fail to Understand the Theory of Evolution. *EvoEdu Outreach* 3,416–419.
- Yeo, S. and Zadnik, M. (2001). Introductory thermal concept evaluation: Assessing students' understanding. *The Physics Teacher*, 39: 496-504.
- Zayton, M. (2014). *Methods of teaching science*. Amman: Dar Alshorok Publication and Distribution.

Author Information

Mohammad Nayef Ayasrah

Associate Professor of Special Education (Talent and Creativity), Al Balqa Applied University/
Department Science of Education, Irbid University
College. Box : Postal code 1293, Irbid, Jordan

Mohareb Ali Alsmadi

Associate Professor of Curriculum and Instruction
AlBalqa Applied University/ Department Science of
Education, Ajloun University College.

Shima' Mkhymryahyaa

Assistant Professor of Curriculum and Instruction Al
Balqa Applied University/ Department Science of
Education, Irbid University College.
